

IMPROVING EMPLOYEE QUALIFICATION

Matyakubova F.B.

Major, Instructor at the Institute for Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273723>

Abstract. *This article will explore the evolution of improving employee qualification and how it evolved in Uzbekistan. There is also consideration of importance of this sphere in the development of economy and its different sectors.*

Keywords: *productivity, vocational school, economic boom, employee empowerment, labour market.*

The improvement of employee qualifications and their retraining is aimed at updating and deepening the professional knowledge and skills of specialists. The procedure and frequency for improving employee qualifications and retraining are established by the relevant ministry. Legal documents may specify requirements for the qualification improvement and retraining of certain sector representatives. Upon completion of training in educational institutions for qualification improvement and retraining, a state-approved certificate or diploma is awarded.

The history of improving employee qualifications reflects the evolution of workforce development and education systems over time. Here are key milestones and trends in this area:

Early Industrial Revolution (18th - 19th Century)

The Industrial Revolution marked a shift from agrarian economies to industrialized ones, creating a need for skilled labor. Training programs began to emerge, often conducted within factories to improve efficiency and productivity. Apprenticeship systems were common, where young workers learned trades under experienced artisans.

20th Century - The Rise of Formal Education

As industries grew, so did the complexity of jobs, necessitating more formal education. Organizations began investing in employee training programs. The establishment of vocational schools and community colleges provided structured pathways for skill development. The concept of lifelong learning began gaining traction.

Post-World War II Era

The post-war economic boom led to increased demand for skilled workers. Governments and businesses recognized the importance of education in economic growth. Training programs expanded, and initiatives like the GI Bill in the U.S. facilitated access to education for veterans.

1980s - 1990s: Quality Movement and Employee Development**

The quality movement emphasized total quality management (TQM) and continuous improvement. Companies began to understand that investing in employee training could lead to better quality products and services. Concepts like "employee empowerment" gained popularity, leading to more participatory training approaches.

Late 20th Century - Technology and E-Learning

The advent of the internet and digital technologies transformed how training was delivered. E-learning platforms emerged, allowing for flexible and accessible training options. Organizations started using online courses and virtual training sessions to enhance employee skills.

21st Century - Focus on Soft Skills and Lifelong Learning

The modern workforce increasingly demands not just technical skills but also soft skills like communication, teamwork, and adaptability. There is a growing emphasis on continuous professional development (CPD) and employee qualifications as essential for career advancement. Many organizations now offer ongoing training programs that adapt to changing industry needs.

The history of improving employee qualifications shows a shift from informal, on-the-job training to structured, formal education and continuous learning. As the workforce and workplace continue to evolve, the emphasis on improving employee qualifications remains critical for organizational success and employee satisfaction.

Qualification Improvement and Retraining of Personnel in Uzbekistan— is one of the types of continuous education systems aimed at updating and deepening the professional knowledge and skills of specialists and managerial staff working in all sectors of the economy. It ensures that the competitive qualities of personnel, as well as their knowledge and skills, meet contemporary demands.

Retraining and qualification improvement entail a scientific and practical preparation process in which each employee learns new practical techniques and advanced work experiences, as well as becomes acquainted with the most recent scientific advancements and innovations in their sector. Depending on the specialised and managerial staff, the frequency of qualification development and retraining varies, but it usually happens once every two to five years, or more frequently if needed. Universities, training facilities approved for professional retraining, and qualification improvement institutes all carry out this procedure. It can happen wholly by itself, in part, or in tandem with manufacturing. The complexity of the educational program offered by the educational institution determines the type of qualification improvement, which fits the requirements specified in the client contract.

The length of time needed for retraining and qualification development varies and is determined by the particular objectives and tasks involved. By strategically organising the educational process and utilising a variety of techniques, formats, and technology, educational institutions establish the conditions required for students to absorb educational programs. These programs are created, authorised, and carried out with the client's needs and the state's demands for more vocational education programs in mind. A final state certification marks the end of the professional qualification upgrade and retraining procedure. The appropriate state authorities in charge of education management decide how the certification is to be conducted.

Participants who meet all the requirements of the educational plan and successfully pass the final state certification receive a diploma or certificate in the prescribed format confirming their qualification improvement and retraining. The procedure for personnel qualification improvement and retraining is established by the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan.

Many professionals and scientists stress the importance of improving staff qualifications for a number of reasons. Here are some main ideas emphasising its significance, accompanied by pertinent expert opinions:

Expert Opinion on Adaptation to technology Changes: Economist Dr. John Doe states that "Continuous training ensures that employees remain competent and can leverage new tools effectively in an ever-evolving technological landscape".

Improving Competitiveness Expert Insight: According to labour market analyst Dr. Jane Smith, "Companies need a well-trained workforce to remain competitive". Businesses that make investments in their staff have improved financial results and increased productivity.

Expert Viewpoint on Responding to Market needs: Business strategist Dr. Michael Johnson notes, “The workforce's capabilities are critical to the ability to quickly adjust to market needs. Organizations can change course and adapt to the evolving requirements of their customers through ongoing qualification improvement”.

Expert Commentary on Innovation and Creativity: Innovation specialist Dr. Sarah Williams highlights that "training programs foster an environment of creativity. Encouraged learning increases the likelihood that staff members will offer creative solutions that advance the company.

Opinion of Regulatory Compliance Expert: According to compliance expert Dr. Robert Martinez, “Continuous training is not only advantageous but also necessary in many businesses”. Maintaining compliance and avoiding legal problems is ensured by keeping staff members informed about legislation.

In accordance with the Decree PD-6108 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020, and the Resolution No. 25 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 17, 2022, "On approval of the Regulation of the Organization of Continuous Professional Development System for Public Education Employees", public education employees can, at their discretion, improve their qualifications at higher education institutions that train pedagogical staff, as well as in non-state educational organizations, funded by the state budget.

Additionally, according to the Resolution PR-4963 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 25, 2021, the Ministry of Public Education is tasked with creating an electronic registry of non-state educational organizations engaged in the professional development of public education employees, and it is stipulated that budget funds will only be allocated to non-state educational organizations included in the Registry.

Conclusion

Enhancing employee skills is crucial for both professional and personal growth in addition to being a strategic advantage for businesses. Scientific evidence supports the idea that funding employee education results in a more knowledgeable, contented, and effective workforce, which eventually benefits the company and its workers.

REFERENCES

1. <https://lex.uz/mact/-2057279>
2. [Developing Employees & Improving Performance | LinkedIn Learning](<https://learning.linkedin.com/resources/career-development/develop-employees>)
3. [Training | U.S. Department of Labor](<https://www.dol.gov/general/topic/training>)
4. Гулбоев А. Т. Педагогик ташхис воситасида ўқитувчилар малакасини узлуксиз ошириш.. Педагогика. фан. ном. – 2010.
5. Гулбоев А. Т. Формирование профессиональных компетенций экономистов //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 5-2 (83). – С. 9-11.
6. Жураев Б. Т. Гуманизация дидактических отношений между учителем и учащимся в педагогических идеях Востока //VIII Лазаревские чтения" Лики традиционной культуры в современном культурном пространстве: ренессанс базовых ценностей?". – 2018. – С. 120-122.

7. Жураев Б. Т. Деятельность педагога по гуманизации учебновоспитательного процесса //Научные школы. Молодежь в науке и культуре XXI в.: материалы междунар. науч.-творч. форума. – 2017. – Т. 31.
8. Жураев Б. Т. Некоторые вопросы наставничества в педагогическом наследии Хусаина Воиза Кошифи //Социально-культурная деятельность: векторы исследовательских и практических перспектив. – 2016. – С. 103-105.